

Quantum Entropy, X-P Covariance and Dynamics

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Sept. 28, 2020

In a previous note, we suggested quantum Shannon's entropy should utilize the probability $a(p_1)\exp(ip_1x)a(p_2)\exp(ip_2x)$ ((1)) which is an addend of spatial density WW where W is the wavefunction. This yields an entropy expression of: $-\int dx W x d/dx W - \sum_p a(p)a(-p)$. The first term is of the form of a covariance of x and average p , but it is also the average information or entropy of an $\exp(ipx)$ type term. In quantum bound states, density is based entirely on joint relative probabilities of conditional momentum probabilities i.e. ((1)). Thus, spatial density is dynamic, while in classical statistical mechanics it is represented by the number of particles in a box at x / volume of the box. The average momentum at a point $x = \sum_p p P(p/x)P(x) = -iWW d \ln(W)/dx$ is also equivalent to: $-i \cdot 5 d/dx (WW)$ i.e. half the change in spatial density. The operator d/dx used to calculate average momentum is the inverse of the position operator x from the point of view of integration by parts. An entropy term of: $-\int dx x d[WW]/dx$ is equivalent to an integral of the density which is 1. Covariance of x and average p at x is a constant regardless of the wavefunction. This covariance, however, is also the portion of Shannon's entropy of a wave $\exp(ipx)$. Thus, the average information of a quantum wave portion (or its entropy) is a constant, regardless of the wavefunction bound system.

Quantum Entropy

We argued in previous notes that the probability term: $a(p_1)\exp(ip_1x)a(p_2)\exp(ip_2x)$ taken from the spatial density $= \sum_{p_1, p_2} a(p_1)\exp(ip_1x)a(p_2)\exp(ip_2x)$ may be used to obtain an expression for entropy, namely:

$$-\int dx W x d/dx W - \sum_p a(p)a(-p) \quad ((2))$$

The first term follows from: $a(p_1)\exp(ip_1x)a(p_2)\exp(ip_2x) \ln[\exp(i(p_1+p_2)x)]$ ((3)) so it is the average information or entropy of a plane wave. ((3)) may be rewritten as:

$$2W(x) \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) ipx = 2 W(x) x d/dx W(x) \quad ((4))$$

It may be noted that $-id \ln(W)/dx =$ average conditional p at x i.e. $\sum_p p P(p/x)$.

The first term of ((2)) is a covariance of x and average p at x i.e. $\sum_p p P(p/x)P(x)$ Where $P(x)=WW$ and $P(p/x)=a(p)\exp(ipx)/W$

$2 W(x) dW/dx$ from ((4)), however, is $d/dx [WW]$ where WW is spatial density, so average momentum at x i.e. $\sum_p p P(p/x)P(x) = -iW d/dx W$ is directly related to the change in spatial density. In classical statistical mechanics, $\sum_p p P(p/x)=0$ because there is equal probability to move forward and backward in a temperature equilibrium. In quantum mechanics, average momentum is directly related to $d/dx [WW]$. This suggests that for WW profiles with

humps (like the oscillator) the derivative is positive moving up a hump and negative moving down, giving an average of 0. Average momentum has positive and negative regions due to the stochastic nature of the potential $V(x) = \sum_k V(k) \exp(ikx)$ even the case of the oscillator where $V(x) = .5kx^2$ only on average.

Consider the case of classical statistical mechanics:

$$d/dx \text{ spatial density} = d/dx \exp(-V(x)/T) = \text{spatial density} * F(x)/T \quad ((5)) \text{ where } F(x) \text{ is force.}$$

In quantum mechanics, things are completely different as: $d/dx \text{ spatial density} = 2 W d/dx W$ or average momentum at $x = \sum_p P(p/x)P(x)$. Only in the case of the ground state oscillator, does one find that $d/dx WW$ is related to force i.e. that of a spring.

Force comes into the picture in the following way which is related to the plane wave $\exp(ipx)$. $\exp(ipx)$ is part of the conditional probability $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ because, it seems, it is imposed by the stochastic potential $V(x) = \sum_k V(k) \exp(ikx)$ where this form is chosen for physical reason i.e. virtual photons.

$$\text{Consider } KE_{ave}(x+b) = \sum_p p^2/2m \exp(ipx)(1+ibp) / \{W(x)(1+b d/dx \ln W)\} \quad ((6))$$

$$= \sum_p p^2/2m \exp(ipx)/W [1+b(ip-i\langle p \rangle)]$$

$$\text{The change in KE ave is: } \sum_p p^2/m \exp(ipx)/W b i (p - \langle p \rangle) \quad ((7))$$

Thus, having a plane wave and $\langle p \rangle$ imposes the form of a change in average kinetic energy KE from x to $x+b$. Next, take the derivative of the Schrodinger equation:

$$-1/2m d/dx \{ d/dx d/dx W / W \} = -1/2m \{ (\sum_p p^2 W) / W - [i\langle p \rangle p^2 W] / W \}$$

$$= -dV/dx = F$$

So ((7)) is equal to force times b i.e. average work. The b portion of $\exp(ip(x+b))$, however, is equivalent to:

$b d/dx \exp(ipx) = b ip \exp(ipx)$ for b small. Thus: $\exp(ipx) \ln(\exp(ipx)) = ip \exp(ipx) = x d/dx \exp(ipx)$. Average momentum ensures that the change in average kinetic energy from x to $x+b$ behaves in such a way that it equals average work done $F(x)b$ with $F(x)$ an average force.

The operator d/dx , which operates on W to yield a term proportional to the average momentum, is the inverse operator of x in terms of integration by parts. Thus, $2 \int x WW dW/dx / W = \int x d/dx [WW]$ and integration by parts yields $\int dx WW = 1$. Thus, even though the average momentum helps to ensure average kinetic energy changes according to $F(x)dx$, its overall information or entropy is 1.

In previous notes, we already noted this, but in this note, we wish to attempt to examine the physical meaning of the term.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that the first term of a proposed entropy expression ((2)) appears to be the covariance of x and $2 \cdot \text{ave momentum} = 2 \cdot \sum \text{over } p P(p/x)P(x)$. $2 \cdot \text{average momentum} = -i\hbar/dx [WW]$ where WW is the spatial density, thus average momentum and change in spatial density are the same. This shows the strong connection between the spatial density and momentum. In fact, spatial density is : $\sum \text{over } p_1, p_2 a(p_1)\exp(ip_1x)a(p_2)\exp(ip_2x)$. A change in density i.e. d/dx acts on $\exp(ipx)$ to bring down a ip . Thus, average momentum and change in density are immediately related. The operator d/dx is the inverse of the position operator x in terms of integration by parts. The covariance of $x\langle p \rangle$ or the average information=entropy is constant for all wavefunctions. The term $\exp(ipx)$ appears as part of the probability expression $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx)/W$ due to the stochastic potential $V(x)=\sum \text{over } k V(k)\exp(ikx)$. It is the form $\exp(ipx)$ which ensures average kinetic energy at a point i.e. $\{\sum \text{over } p p^2/2m P(p/x)\} / W(x)$ changes according to $F(x)dx$ i.e. the average work done as shown above.